

ADME parameters of the investigated Oseltamivir derivatives.

Compound	GI Absorption	BBB Permeability	Pgp Substrate	Cyp Inhibition	log Kp (cm/s)
Os-Phe	High	No	Yes	No	-9.31
Os-Il	High	No	Yes	No	-9.46
Os-Ser	Low	No	Yes	No	-10.82
Os-Tyr	Low	No	Yes	No	-9.66
Os-Phe-Hydroxamate	Low	No	Yes	No	-8.31
Os-Il-Hydroxamate	Low	No	Yes	No	-8.46
Os-Ser-Hydroxamate	Low	No	Yes	No	-9.81
Os-Tyr-Hydroxamate	Low	No	Yes	No	-8.66
Oseltamivir	High	No	Yes	No	-7.42

Figure 4. BOILED EGG – for the target compounds (S1-S8)

Yellow ovule (yolk): are compounds predicted to passively permeate through BBB.

White ovule (white): are compounds predicted to be passively absorbed by the GIT.

PGP+: Blue dots for compounds to be substrate for P-glycoprotein.

SMILES CCC(OC1C=C(CC(C1NC(=O)C)N)C(=O)N[C@H](C(=O)O)Cc1ccccc1)CC

Physicochemical Properties	
Formula	C23H33N3O5
Molecular weight	431.53 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	31
Num. arom. heavy atoms	6
Fraction Csp3	0.52
Num. rotatable bonds	12
Num. H-bond acceptors	6
Num. H-bond donors	4
Molar Refractivity	117.30
TPSA	130.75 Å²
Lipophilicity	
Log P_{ow} (ILOGP)	2.41
Log P_{ow} (XLOGP3)	-0.53
Log P_{ow} (WLOGP)	1.53
Log P_{ow} (MLOGP)	0.71
Log P_{ow} (SILICOS-IT)	1.83
Consensus Log P_{ow}	1.19

Water Solubility	
Log S (ESOL)	-1.53
Solubility	1.27e+01 mg/ml ; 2.93e-02 mol/l
Class	Very soluble
Log S (All)	-1.75
Solubility	7.73e+00 mg/ml ; 1.79e-02 mol/l
Class	Very soluble
Log S (SILICOS-IT)	-4.25
Solubility	2.44e-02 mg/ml ; 5.66e-05 mol/l
Class	Moderately soluble
Pharmacokinetics	
GI absorption	High
BBB permeant	No
P-gp substrate	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No
Log K_p (skin permeation)	-9.31 cm/s
Druglikeness	
Lipinski	Yes; 0 violation
Ghose	Yes
Weber	No; 1 violation: Rotors>10
Egan	Yes
Muegge	Yes
Bioavailability Score	0.55
Medicinal Chemistry	
PAINS	0 alert
Brenk	0 alert
Leadlikeness	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7
Synthetic accessibility	5.01

ADME parameters of Oseltamivir-Phenylalanine

SMILES CCC(OC1C=C(CC(C1NC(=O)C)N)C(=O)NC(=O)NO)Cc1ccccc1)CC

Physicochemical Properties	
Formula	C23H34N4O5
Molecular weight	446.54 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	32
Num. arom. heavy atoms	6
Fraction Csp3	0.52
Num. rotatable bonds	13
Num. H-bond acceptors	6
Num. H-bond donors	5
Molar Refractivity	119.26
TPSA	142.78 Å²
Lipophilicity	
Log P_{ow} (ILOGP)	1.51
Log P_{ow} (XLOGP3)	1.01
Log P_{ow} (WLOGP)	0.96
Log P_{ow} (MLOGP)	0.33
Log P_{ow} (SILICOS-IT)	1.07
Consensus Log P_{ow}	0.98

Water Solubility	
Log S (ESOL)	-2.53
Solubility	1.33e+00 mg/ml ; 2.98e-03 mol/l
Class	Soluble
Log S (All)	-3.60
Solubility	1.13e-01 mg/ml ; 2.53e-04 mol/l
Class	Soluble
Log S (SILICOS-IT)	-4.28
Solubility	2.32e-02 mg/ml ; 5.20e-05 mol/l
Class	Moderately soluble
Pharmacokinetics	
GI absorption	Low
BBB permeant	No
P-gp substrate	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No
Log K_p (skin permeation)	-8.31 cm/s
Druglikeness	
Lipinski	Yes; 0 violation
Ghose	Yes
Weber	No; 2 violations: Rotors>10, TPSA>140
Egan	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6
Muegge	Yes
Bioavailability Score	0.55
Medicinal Chemistry	
PAINS	0 alert
Brenk	2 alerts: hydroxamic_acid, oxygen-nitrogen_single_bond
Leadlikeness	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7
Synthetic accessibility	5.17

ADME parameters of Oseltamivir-Phenylalanine-Hydroxamate

Molecule 1

SMILES CCC(OC1C=C(CC(C1NC(=O)C)N)C(=O)O)CC

Physicochemical Properties

Formula	C14H24N2O4
Molecular weight	284.35 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	20
Num. arom. heavy atoms	0
Fraction Csp3	0.71
Num. rotatable bonds	7
Num. H-bond acceptors	5
Num. H-bond donors	3
Molar Refractivity	75.39
TPSA [?]	101.65 Å ²

Lipophilicity

Log $P_{o/w}$ (iLOGP) [?]	1.95
Log $P_{o/w}$ (XLOGP3) [?]	-1.87
Log $P_{o/w}$ (WLOGP) [?]	0.81
Log $P_{o/w}$ (MLOGP) [?]	0.12
Log $P_{o/w}$ (SILICOS-IT) [?]	0.37
Consensus Log $P_{o/w}$ [?]	0.28

Water Solubility

Log S (ESOL) [?]	0.04
Solubility	3.10e+02 mg/ml ; 1.09e+00 mol/l
Class [?]	Highly soluble
Log S (Ali) [?]	0.25
Solubility	5.11e+02 mg/ml ; 1.80e+00 mol/l
Class [?]	Highly soluble
Log S (SILICOS-IT) [?]	-1.38
Solubility	1.19e+01 mg/ml ; 4.19e-02 mol/l
Class [?]	Soluble

Pharmacokinetics

GI absorption [?]	High
BBB permeant [?]	No
P-gp substrate [?]	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor [?]	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor [?]	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor [?]	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor [?]	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor [?]	No
Log K_p (skin permeation) [?]	-9.36 cm/s

Druglikeness

Lipinski [?]	Yes; 0 violation
Ghose [?]	Yes
Veber [?]	Yes
Egan [?]	Yes
Muegge [?]	Yes
Bioavailability Score [?]	0.55

Medicinal Chemistry

PAINS [?]	0 alert
Brenk [?]	0 alert
Leadlikeness [?]	Yes
Synthetic accessibility [?]	4.24

Molecule 1

SMILES CCC(OC1C=C(CC(C1NC(=O)C)N)C(=O)NC(C(CC)C)C(=O)O)CC

Physicochemical Properties

Formula	C ₂₀ H ₃₅ N ₃ O ₅
Molecular weight	397.51 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	28
Num. arom. heavy atoms	0
Fraction Csp ³	0.75
Num. rotatable bonds	12
Num. H-bond acceptors	6
Num. H-bond donors	4
Molar Refractivity	107.23
TPSA [?]	130.75 Å ²

Lipophilicity

Log <i>P</i> _{o/w} (iLOGP) [?]	2.47
Log <i>P</i> _{o/w} (XLOGP3) [?]	-0.80
Log <i>P</i> _{o/w} (WLOGP) [?]	1.34
Log <i>P</i> _{o/w} (MLOGP) [?]	0.30
Log <i>P</i> _{o/w} (SILICOS-IT) [?]	1.32
Consensus Log <i>P</i> _{o/w} [?]	0.93

Water Solubility	
Log S (ESOL) [?]	-1.01
Solubility	3.90e+01 mg/ml ; 9.80e-02 mol/l
Class [?]	Very soluble
Log S (Ali) [?]	-1.47
Solubility	1.36e+01 mg/ml ; 3.41e-02 mol/l
Class [?]	Very soluble
Log S (SILICOS-IT) [?]	-2.58
Solubility	1.04e+00 mg/ml ; 2.61e-03 mol/l
Class [?]	Soluble

Pharmacokinetics

GI absorption [?]	High
BBB permeant [?]	No
P-gp substrate [?]	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor [?]	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor [?]	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor [?]	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor [?]	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor [?]	No
Log <i>K</i> _p (skin permeation) [?]	-9.29 cm/s

Druglikeness

Lipinski [?]	Yes; 0 violation
Ghose [?]	Yes
Veber [?]	No; 1 violation: Rotors>10
Egan [?]	Yes
Muegge [?]	Yes
Bioavailability Score [?]	0.55

Medicinal Chemistry

PAINS [?]	0 alert
Brenk [?]	0 alert
Leadlikeness [?]	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7
Synthetic accessibility [?]	5.28

Molecule 2

SMILES CCC(OC1C=C(CC(C1NC(=O)C)N)C(=O)NC(C(=O)NO)C(CC)C)CC

Physicochemical Properties

Formula	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₅
Molecular weight	412.52 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	29
Num. arom. heavy atoms	0
Fraction Csp ³	0.75
Num. rotatable bonds	13
Num. H-bond acceptors	6
Num. H-bond donors	5
Molar Refractivity	109.19
TPSA	142.78 Å ²

Lipophilicity

Log $P_{o/w}$ (iLOGP)	2.41
Log $P_{o/w}$ (XLOGP3)	0.74
Log $P_{o/w}$ (WLOGP)	0.76
Log $P_{o/w}$ (MLOGP)	-0.07
Log $P_{o/w}$ (SILICOS-IT)	0.58
Consensus Log $P_{o/w}$	0.88

Water Solubility

Log S (ESOL)	-2.01
Solubility	4.07e+00 mg/ml ; 9.87e-03 mol/l
Class	Soluble
Log S (Ali)	-3.32
Solubility	1.99e-01 mg/ml ; 4.81e-04 mol/l
Class	Soluble
Log S (SILICOS-IT)	-2.62
Solubility	9.85e-01 mg/ml ; 2.39e-03 mol/l
Class	Soluble

Pharmacokinetics

GI absorption	Low
BBB permeant	No
P-gp substrate	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No

Cytochrome P450 2D6 inhibitor: SVM model built on 3664 molecules (training set) and tested on 1068 molecules (test set)
10-fold CV: ACC=0.79 / AUC=0.85
External: ACC=0.81 / AUC=0.87

Ghose	Yes
Veber	No; 2 violations: Rotors>10, TPSA>140
Egan	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6
Muegge	Yes
Bioavailability Score	0.55

Medicinal Chemistry

PAINS	0 alert
Brenk	2 alerts: hydroxamic_acid, oxygen-nitrogen_single_bond
Leadlikeness	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7
Synthetic accessibility	5.46

SMILES CCC(OC1C=C(CC(C1NC(=O)C)N)C(=O)N[C@H](C(=O)O)Cc1ccccc1)CC

Physicochemical Properties

Formula	C23H33N3O5
Molecular weight	431.53 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	31
Num. arom. heavy atoms	6
Fraction Csp3	0.52
Num. rotatable bonds	12
Num. H-bond acceptors	6
Num. H-bond donors	4
Molar Refractivity	117.30
TPSA	130.75 Å²

Lipophilicity

Log P_{ow} (ILOGP)	2.41
Log P_{ow} (XLOGP3)	-0.53
Log P_{ow} (WLOGP)	1.53
Log P_{ow} (MLOGP)	0.71
Log P_{ow} (SILICOS-IT)	1.83
Consensus Log P_{ow}	1.19

Water Solubility

Log S (ESOL)	-1.53
Solubility	1.27e+01 mg/ml ; 2.93e-02 mol/l
Class	Very soluble
Log S (All)	-1.75
Solubility	7.73e+00 mg/ml ; 1.79e-02 mol/l
Class	Very soluble
Log S (SILICOS-IT)	-4.25
Solubility	2.44e-02 mg/ml ; 5.66e-05 mol/l
Class	Moderately soluble

Pharmacokinetics

GI absorption	High
BBB permeant	No
P-gp substrate	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No
Log K_p (skin permeation)	-9.31 cm/s

Druglikeness

Lipinski	Yes; 0 violation
Ghose	Yes
Veber	No; 1 violation: Rotors>10
Egan	Yes
Muegge	Yes
Bioavailability Score	0.55

Medicinal Chemistry

PAINS	0 alert
Brenk	0 alert
Leadlikeness	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7
Synthetic accessibility	5.01

Os-Phe

SMILES CCC(OC1C=C(CC(C1NC(=O)C)N)C(=O)NC(C(=O)NO)Cc1ccccc1)
CC

Physicochemical Properties

Formula	C23H34N4O5
Molecular weight	446.54 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	32
Num. arom. heavy atoms	6
Fraction Csp3	0.52
Num. rotatable bonds	13
Num. H-bond acceptors	6
Num. H-bond donors	5
Molar Refractivity	119.26
TPSA	142.78 Å²

Lipophilicity

Log P_{ow} (iLOGP)	1.51
Log P_{ow} (XLOGP3)	1.01
Log P_{ow} (WLOGP)	0.96
Log P_{ow} (MLOGP)	0.33
Log P_{ow} (SILICOS-IT)	1.07
Consensus Log P_{ow}	0.98

Water Solubility

Log S (ESOL)	-2.53
Solubility	1.33e+00 mg/ml ; 2.98e-03 mol/l
Class	Soluble
Log S (Ali)	-3.60
Solubility	1.13e-01 mg/ml ; 2.53e-04 mol/l
Class	Soluble
Log S (SILICOS-IT)	-4.28
Solubility	2.32e-02 mg/ml ; 5.20e-05 mol/l
Class	Moderately soluble

Pharmacokinetics

GI absorption	Low
BBB permeant	No
P-gp substrate	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No
Log K_p (skin permeation)	-8.31 cm/s

Druglikeness

Lipinski	Yes; 0 violation
Ghose	Yes
Veber	No; 2 violations: Rotors>10, TPSA>140
Egan	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6
Muegge	Yes
Bioavailability Score	0.55

Medicinal Chemistry

PAINS	0 alert
Brenk	2 alerts: hydroxamic_acid, oxygen-nitrogen_single_bond
Leadlikeness	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7
Synthetic accessibility	5.17

Os-Phe-Hydroxamate

SMILES CCC(OC1C=C(CC(C1NC(=O)C)N)C(=O)N[C@H](C(=O)O)CO)CC

Physicochemical Properties

Formula	C17H29N3O6
Molecular weight	371.43 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	26
Num. arom. heavy atoms	0
Fraction Csp3	0.71
Num. rotatable bonds	11
Num. H-bond acceptors	7
Num. H-bond donors	5
Molar Refractivity	93.97
TPSA	150.98 Å²

Lipophilicity

Log $P_{0/w}$ (iLOGP)	1.44
Log $P_{0/w}$ (XLOGP3)	-3.17
Log $P_{0/w}$ (WLOGP)	-0.72
Log $P_{0/w}$ (MLOGP)	-1.18
Log $P_{0/w}$ (SILICOS-IT)	-0.33
Consensus Log $P_{0/w}$	-0.79

Water Solubility

Log S (ESOL)	0.58
Solubility	1.41e+03 mg/ml ; 3.80e+00 mol/l
Class	Highly soluble
Log S (Ali)	0.57
Solubility	1.37e+03 mg/ml ; 3.70e+00 mol/l
Class	Highly soluble
Log S (SILICOS-IT)	-1.21
Solubility	2.31e+01 mg/ml ; 6.21e-02 mol/l
Class	Soluble

Pharmacokinetics

GI absorption	Low
BBB permeant	No
P-gp substrate	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No
Log K_p (skin permeation)	-10.82 cm/s

Druglikeness

Lipinski	Yes; 0 violation
Ghose	No; 1 violation: WLOGP<-0.4
Veber	No; 2 violations: Rotors>10, TPSA>140
Egan	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6
Muegge	No; 2 violations: XLOGP3<-2, TPSA>150
Bioavailability Score	0.55

Medicinal Chemistry

PAINS	0 alert
Brenk	0 alert
Leadlikeness	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7
Synthetic accessibility	4.89

Os-Ser

SMILES OCC(C(=O)NO)NC(=O)C1=CC(C(C(=O)N)NC(=O)C)OC(C)CC

Physicochemical Properties

Formula	C17H30N4O6
Molecular weight	386.44 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	27
Num. arom. heavy atoms	0
Fraction Csp3	0.71
Num. rotatable bonds	12
Num. H-bond acceptors	7
Num. H-bond donors	6
Molar Refractivity	95.93
TPSA	163.01 Å²

Lipophilicity

Log P_{olw} (ILOGP)	1.48
Log P_{olw} (XLOGP3)	-1.63
Log P_{olw} (WLOGP)	-1.30
Log P_{olw} (MLOGP)	-1.54
Log P_{olw} (SILICOS-IT)	-1.07
Consensus Log P_{olw}	-0.81

Water Solubility	
Log S (ESOL)	-0.42
Solubility	1.48e+02 mg/ml ; 3.83e-01 mol/l
Class	Very soluble
Log S (Ali)	-1.28
Solubility	2.01e+01 mg/ml ; 5.21e-02 mol/l
Class	Very soluble
Log S (SILICOS-IT)	-1.25
Solubility	2.19e+01 mg/ml ; 5.66e-02 mol/l
Class	Soluble
Pharmacokinetics	
GI absorption	Low
BBB permeant	No
P-gp substrate	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No
Log K_p (skin permeation)	-9.81 cm/s
Druglikeness	
Lipinski	Yes; 1 violation: NHorOH>5
Ghose	No; 1 violation: WLOGP<-0.4
Veber	No; 2 violations: Rotors>10, TPSA>140
Egan	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6
Muegge	No; 2 violations: TPSA>150, H-don>5
Bioavailability Score	0.55
Medicinal Chemistry	
PAINS	0 alert
Brenk	2 alerts: hydroxamic_acid, oxygen-nitrogen_single_bond
Leadlikeness	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7
Synthetic accessibility	5.05

Os-Ser-Hydroxamate

SMILES CCC(OC1C=C(CC(C1NC(=O)N)C(=O)N[C@H](C(=O)O)Cc1ccc(cc1)O)CC

Physicochemical Properties	
Formula	C23H33N3O6
Molecular weight	447.52 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	32
Num. arom. heavy atoms	6
Fraction Csp3	0.52
Num. rotatable bonds	12
Num. H-bond acceptors	7
Num. H-bond donors	5
Molar Refractivity	119.32
TPSA	150.98 Å²
Lipophilicity	
Log P_{0W} (iLOGP)	2.00
Log P_{0W} (XLOGP3)	-0.89
Log P_{0W} (WLOGP)	1.24
Log P_{0W} (MLOGP)	0.20
Log P_{0W} (SILICOS-IT)	1.37
Consensus Log P_{0W}	0.78

Water Solubility	
Log S (ESOL)	-1.40
Solubility	1.78e+01 mg/ml ; 3.97e-02 mol/l
Class	Very soluble
Log S (Ali)	-1.80
Solubility	7.12e+00 mg/ml ; 1.59e-02 mol/l
Class	Very soluble
Log S (SILICOS-IT)	-3.66
Solubility	9.88e-02 mg/ml ; 2.21e-04 mol/l
Class	Soluble
Pharmacokinetics	
GI absorption	Low
BBB permeant	No
P-gp substrate	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No
Log K_p (skin permeation)	-9.66 cm/s
Druglikeness	
Lipinski	Yes; 0 violation
Ghose	Yes
Weber	No; 2 violations: Rotors>10, TPSA>140
Egan	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6
Muegge	No; 1 violation: TPSA>150
Bioavailability Score	0.55
Medicinal Chemistry	
PAINS	0 alert
Brenk	0 alert
Leadlikeness	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7
Synthetic accessibility	5.02

Os-Tyr

SMILES CCC(OC1C=C(CC(C1NC(=O)C)N)C(=O)NC(C(=O)NO)Cc1ccc(cc1)O)CC

Physicochemical Properties

Formula	C23H34N4O6
Molecular weight	462.54 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	33
Num. arom. heavy atoms	6
Fraction Csp3	0.52
Num. rotatable bonds	13
Num. H-bond acceptors	7
Num. H-bond donors	6
Molar Refractivity	121.28
TPSA	163.01 Å²

Lipophilicity

Log P_{OW} (ILOGP)	2.09
Log P_{OW} (XLOGP3)	0.65
Log P_{OW} (WLOGP)	0.66
Log P_{OW} (MLOGP)	-0.17
Log P_{OW} (SILICOS-IT)	0.61
Consensus Log P_{OW}	0.77

Water Solubility

Log S (ESOL)	-2.39
Solubility	1.87e+00 mg/ml ; 4.04e-03 mol/l
Class	Soluble
Log S (Ali)	-3.65
Solubility	1.04e-01 mg/ml ; 2.24e-04 mol/l
Class	Soluble
Log S (SILICOS-IT)	-3.69
Solubility	9.38e-02 mg/ml ; 2.03e-04 mol/l
Class	Soluble

Pharmacokinetics

GI absorption	Low
BBB permeant	No
P-gp substrate	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No
Log K_p (skin permeation)	-8.66 cm/s

Druglikeness

Lipinski	Yes; 1 violation: NHorOH>5
Ghose	Yes
Veber	No; 2 violations: Rotors>10, TPSA>140
Egan	No; 1 violation: TPSA>131.6
Muegge	No; 2 violations: TPSA>150, H-don>5
Bioavailability Score	0.55

Medicinal Chemistry

PAINS	0 alert
Brenk	2 alerts: hydroxamic_acid, oxygen-nitrogen_single_bond
Leadlikeness	No; 2 violations: MW>350, Rotors>7
Synthetic accessibility	5.18

Os-Tyr-Hydroxamate